

1 **Dust storms increase the tolerance of phytoplankton to**
2 **thermal and pH changes**

3 **Running title: Dust increases phytoplankton tolerance**

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14 Reviewed version: September 27th, 2023

15 **Abstract**

16 Aquatic communities are increasingly subjected to multiple stressors through global
17 change, including warming, pH shifts, and elevated nutrient concentrations. These
18 stressors often surpass species tolerance range, leading to unpredictable consequences for
19 aquatic communities and ecosystem functioning. Phytoplankton, as the foundation of the
20 aquatic food web, play a crucial role in controlling water quality and the transfer of
21 nutrients and energy to higher trophic levels. Despite the significance in understanding
22 the effect of multiple stressors, further research is required to explore the combined
23 impact of multiple stressors on phytoplankton. In this study, we used a combination of
24 crossed experiment and mechanistic model to analyze the ecological and biogeochemical
25 effects of global change on aquatic ecosystems and to forecast phytoplankton dynamics.

26 We examined the effect of dust (0-75 mg L⁻¹), temperature (19-27°C), and pH (6.3-7.3)
27 on the growth rate of the algal species *Scenedesmus obliquus*. Further, we carried out a
28 geospatial analysis to identify regions of the planet where aquatic systems could be most
29 affected by atmospheric dust deposition. Our mechanistic model and our empirical data
30 show that dust exerts a positive effect on phytoplankton growth rate, broadening its
31 thermal and pH tolerance range. Finally, our geospatial analysis identifies several high-
32 risk areas including the highlands of the Tibetan Plateau, western United States, South
33 America, central and southern Africa, central Australia as well as the Mediterranean
34 region where dust-induced changes are expected to have the greatest impacts. Overall,
35 our study shows that increasing dust storms associated with a more arid climate and land
36 degradation can reverse the negative effects of high temperatures and low pH on
37 phytoplankton growth, affecting the biogeochemistry of aquatic ecosystems and their role
38 in the cycles of the elements and tolerance to global change.

39

40 **Keywords (6-10):** Dust, Aerosol deposition, Phytoplankton Dynamic, Growth rate,
41 Mechanistic model, Temperature, pH, Interactive effects

1. Introduction

Global change is leading to environmental conditions that exceed species tolerance ranges, resulting in unpredictable impacts on ecological communities and ecosystem functioning (Henson et al., 2021; Saavedra et al., 2013). As a result, there is a growing need to comprehensively assess the co-occurring environmental pressures at different levels of biological organization. However, few studies have targeted the effect of multiple stressors on population growth and fitness. Although understanding how individual factors influence population dynamics is vital, applying the findings to the actual world presents challenges (Orr et al., 2020). In the natural world, populations are concurrently affected by physical characteristics such as temperature and light, as well as biological factors such as predation, and chemical conditions including nutrient availability, pH, and others. These factors not only affect the dynamics of individual populations but also the communities in which they live (Kozik et al., 2019; Reynolds, 1984).

Understanding the impacts of multiple stressors is critical for primary producers, the organisms found at the base of trophic food webs. Phytoplankton, the primary producers in the pelagic zone of oceans and lakes, account for approximately half the global annual photoproduction and play a pivotal role in global biogeochemical cycles and the Earth's climate through the sequestration of carbon into freshwater and marine sediments (Falkowski et al., 2008; Mahowald et al., 2017). Production from phytoplankton is also disproportionately affected by human activities such as climate change, acidification, and pollution in both marine and freshwater environments, resulting in significant fluctuations in their growth conditions (Behrenfeld et al., 2006). Although numerous empirical studies have investigated the single and interactive effects of environmental factors and

67 phytoplankton structure, ecology and/or physiology (e.g. Anderson et al., 2022; Elliott et
68 al., 2006), performing experiments under multiple driving environmental conditions is
69 necessary to develop tools for forecasting phytoplankton dynamics in a changing climate
70 (Baird & Emsley, 1999; Thomas et al., 2017).

71

72 Nutrient availability and temperature are key environmental factors that control
73 phytoplankton growth and they can act synergistically, stimulating algal growth
74 (Fernández-González et al., 2022) by increasing metabolic, growth, and reproductive
75 rates (Reinl et al., 2022). The growth curve of phytoplankton species and their responses
76 to environmental nutrients can be represented by a saturation relationship (See supporting
77 information, Figure S1a) that is theoretically described by Monod kinetics (Monod,
78 1949). Likewise, multiple studies have shown that temperature plays a crucial role in
79 influencing chemical reaction rates, metabolism and growth rate in ectothermic
80 organisms, including phytoplankton. The temperature-controlled reaction rates conform
81 to an exponential curve until they reach the optimum temperature (See supporting
82 information, Figure S1b), a pattern shared from unicellular microbes to plants and animals
83 (Gillooly et al., 2001). The effect of temperature on the growth of ectotherms follows an
84 asymmetric curve characterized by unimodality and left skewness (Eppley, 1972;
85 Kingsolver, 2009), which has biological and ecological implications as ectotherms are
86 more sensitive to warming than cooling (Martin & Huey, 2008). In the context of global
87 warming, this can lead to an increase in the risk of extinction for some species (Dillon et
88 al., 2010). Some studies have shown that nutrients can influence the thermal tolerance
89 curves of species, modifying the characteristics of the curve. Given that metabolic rates
90 determine the rate at which resources are acquired from the environment and used for
91 biological processes, it stands to reason that higher growth rates resulting from warming

92 can only be sustained if sufficient nutrients are available. Maddux and Jones (1964) and
93 Bestion et al. (2018) showed that the optimum growth temperature of some phytoplankton
94 species, as well as their thermal range of growth, are higher or broader under high nutrient
95 than under low nutrient conditions. However, these authors used chemical nutrients in
96 their experiments, and thus it remains to be seen whether actual sources of nutrients
97 associated with increasingly recurrent and intense events, such as atmospheric dust storms
98 that are related to droughts and desertification (Javadian et al., 2019; Lambert et al.,
99 2020), also have the ability to modify species tolerance ranges.

100

101 The role of global dust production in providing nutrients to the marine environment and
102 resulting climate feedbacks on millennial timescales are well-established phenomena
103 (Lambert et al., 2008). However, human activities and climate change have significantly
104 increased the dust-mediated transport of nutrients to marine and freshwater environments,
105 which has measurable impacts on seasonal, annual, and decadal timescales (Brahney et
106 al., 2015a; Brahney et al., 2014; Cabrerizo et al., 2016; Mladenov et al., 2011). Dust
107 contains a variety of both macro- and micro-nutrients, the availability of which in
108 freshwater environments is controlled by the source composition and changes during
109 atmospheric transport, as well as conditions in the receiving environment, including pH
110 and attendant nutrient limitation (Brahney et al., 2021; Stockdale et al., 2016). Modern
111 dust derived from industrial, urban, combustion, and agricultural sources is likely to
112 contain more phosphorus than historical dust, which has led to an approximate 40%
113 increase in dust-P deposition (Brahney et al., 2015b). In addition, studies have shown that
114 low pH of atmospheric moisture can increase the solubilization of apatite mineral in dust,
115 enhancing the bioavailability of P (Baker et al., 2021; Nenes et al., 2011). However,
116 acidification can affect the acid base balance in phytoplankton and the efficacy of

117 phosphatase enzymes (Flynn et al., 2012; Rost et al., 2003), which can lead to reduced
118 primary production and growth (Gerloff-Elias et al., 2005). Hinga (2002) and Hansen
119 (2002) reported that the growth rate of phytoplankton generally had a unimodal
120 relationship with pH values (See supporting information, Figure S1c), with the optimal
121 pH being species-dependent. Therefore, studying how ecosystem pH affects nutrient
122 release from dust at different temperatures and their interactive impact on phytoplankton
123 functional traits represents a novel approach.

124

125 Because of the complex factors that affect the dynamics of phytoplankton populations,
126 mechanistic models are a particularly useful tool for analyzing the ecological and
127 biogeochemical effects of global change on aquatic ecosystems (Longhurst et al., 1995;
128 Medvinsky et al., 2019). These models, combined with empirical data, can be used to
129 forecast phytoplankton dynamics. Here, we develop a semi-empirical model explaining
130 the role of pH affecting the nutrient release from dust and a mechanistic model that
131 incorporates the effect of dust, temperature, and pH on the growth rate of a
132 phytoplanktonic species (*Scenedesmus obliquus*). We use a common freshwater algal
133 species and fit a tolerance function that is dependent on these three factors. We decided
134 to work with a freshwater model species, given that these ecosystems are particularly
135 vulnerable to global change, including the effects of dust, warming, and spatio-temporal
136 variations of pH (Woodward et al., 2009, 2010). Our aim is to present an individual
137 mechanistic model that builds upon previous models (e.g. Briere et al., 1999; Monod,
138 1949; Thomas et al., 2017) and to test it empirically. This represents a critical step in
139 understanding the impacts of multiple environmental stressors, including realistic sources
140 of nutrients, in the analysis of global change on the growth of a model species of
141 freshwater phytoplankton.

142

143 **Model description**

144 Our model of population growth for phytoplankton is based on the nutrient availability
145 (measured as phosphorus, [P]) released by dust, temperature and pH. First, using
146 experimental data, we build a novel semi-empirical model that allows us to describe the
147 release of P from dust at different pH and temperatures (Nutrient model), assuming that
148 P is the main limiting nutrient in our phytoplankton population and will have a greater
149 effect on population growth. Next, we introduce a mechanistic model of population
150 growth for phytoplankton (Growth model) based on the availability of phosphorus
151 obtained in the Nutrient model, temperature, and pH. Both models are described in detail
152 below.

153 Nutrient model

154 Our semi-empirical model predicts the concentration of nutrients (phosphorus) in the
155 environment based on theoretical considerations, with experimentally determined
156 constants (see Table S1). We establish that final P concentration depends on initial P
157 concentration (P_0 , in $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), dust concentration added to the medium (Du , in mg L^{-1}),
158 pH, and temperature (T , in $^{\circ}\text{C}$).

159 Assuming that final P is the result of the equilibrium of a chemical reaction,

$$160 \quad P = P_0 + \frac{k_1}{k_2} Du, \quad (1)$$

161 where k_1 and k_2 are the forward and backward rate constants of the reaction. We also
162 assume that the balance between forward and backward rates is sigmoidal with the
163 exponent depending directly on pH and is sensitive to temperature via an Arrhenius
164 function, as follows:

$$165 \quad P = P_0 + \alpha \frac{Du}{1 + \exp\left(\beta_1 + \beta_2 \text{pH} - \frac{\beta_3}{T + 273}\right)}, \quad (2)$$

166 where α is the maximum yield of P from dust, β_1 is a parameter controlling the location
 167 of the inflection point at nominal pH and temperature, β_2 captures the sensitivity to pH
 168 and β_3 is proportional to the activation energy in the Arrhenius model (see values of
 169 parameters in Table S1). This model is fitted to the available phosphorus in our
 170 experiment 24 hours after dust addition ($R^2 = 0.903$; see Figure 1a,b).

171 Growth model

172 The net population growth rate (μ) can be described as the difference between the cell
 173 division rate and the death rate in the population (similar to Thomas et al., 2017). We
 174 assume that growth (g) is positively controlled by: a) increasing temperature (T) until
 175 reaching the optimum; b) availability of nutrients released by dust follows a saturation
 176 curve; and, c) optimal pH range follows a unimodal curve. The death rate (d) in the
 177 population is controlled by: a) supra-optimal temperature; and, b) pH above or below the
 178 optimum:

179
$$\mu = g(T, Du, pH) - d(T, pH). \quad (3)$$

180 We describe the control of nutrients on growth (g) through the Monod equation:

181
$$g = b(T) \times \frac{P}{P+K}, \quad (4)$$

182 where $b(T)$ is a thermal rate function, P is the available phosphorus concentration
 183 according to equation 2, and K is the half-saturation constant for uptake of phosphorus
 184 that depends on temperature and pH,

185
$$K = c_1 \exp[c_2 (\Delta pH) + c_3 (\Delta T)], \quad (5)$$

186 where c_1 is the half-saturation value in nominal conditions and the other two c_j reflect the
 187 unknown sensitivity of the half saturation value to pH and temperature (see values in
 188 Table S2). ΔpH and ΔT represent the variation in pH and temperature with respect to the
 189 optimal pH (pH-7.3) and temperature (T-23) for our species, respectively.

190 For the thermal rate function we follow the temperature-dependent model for ectotherms
191 proposed by Briere et al. (1999),

$$192 \quad b(T) = aT \times (T - T_b) \sqrt{T_m - T} \quad \text{and } b(t) = 0 \text{ if } T < T_b \text{ or } T > T_m, \quad (6)$$

193 where T_b and T_m are lower and upper thresholds, respectively. To make the curve more
194 stable during estimation we rescale following (Wangen, 2021), and introduce nutrient
195 dependence to the upper threshold. This gives

$$196 \quad b(T, P) = b_1 T \times (T - T_b) \sqrt{1 - \frac{T}{(b_2 + b_3 P)}}, \quad (7)$$

197 where b_1 is the change in the reproduction rate with increasing temperature, b_2 is the base
198 upper threshold for T_m , and b_3 is the nutrient increase rate for T_m .

199 Finally, we assume that death rate increases exponentially with temperature, and we also
200 include the possibility that death rates may increase with pH deviation from optimal,
201 giving

$$202 \quad d(T, pH) = d_0 + d_1 \exp[-d_2(\Delta pH)^2 + d_3(\Delta T)]. \quad (8)$$

203 Here d_0 is the baseline of mortality rate across environmental conditions, d_1 is the
204 additional rate of mortality away from nominal conditions, and d_2 and d_3 reflect the
205 acceleration of death rate due to suboptimal pH and temperature, respectively.

206 The growth model is fit to the growth rate data from our experiment ($R^2 = 0.691$; see
207 Figure 1c) and the result of the Growth model is represented in Figure 2.

208

209 **2. Material and Methods**

210 **Culture conditions**

211 The ubiquitous phytoplanktonic species *Scenedesmus obliquus* was obtained from the
212 University of Texas-UTEX Culture Collection of Algae. We chose this species due to its
213 wide geographical distribution, including oligo-meso-eutrophic systems (Johnson et al.,

214 2007; Naumann, 1927; Sánchez-Castillo, 1988; Talib et al., 2008; Tas & Gonulol, 2007;
215 Tolotti, 2001), fresh and brackish waters (An et al., 1999; Redden & Rukminasari, 2008),
216 and its ecologically significant role, constituting a significant portion of the biomass of
217 phytoplanktonic green algae (Van Vuuren et al., 2006; Yuan et al., 2023). It was cultured
218 under non-axenic conditions in diluted Bold's Basal Medium (BBM), with a limited P
219 supply and a concentration of approximately $2 \mu\text{g P L}^{-1}$. *S. obliquus* was cultured in a
220 Conviron CMP6060 Environmental Chamber (Winnipeg, Manitoba, Canada) under a
221 regulated temperature of 19°C . It was exposed to $\sim 120 \mu\text{mol photon m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ of a cool
222 white fluorescent light under a 12:12 h photoperiod.

223

224 Prior to the experiment, *S. obliquus* was acclimated to three temperature treatments [low
225 (19°C), medium (23°C) and high (27°C) temperature] in environmental chambers and
226 three pH levels (6.3, 6.8 and 7.3), for at least five generations. The pH was maintained
227 constant using 0.5 M piperazine-N,N'-bis(2-ethanesulfonic acid) (PIPES) buffer in order
228 to prevent pH changes after the addition of dust that could hinder the interpretation of the
229 results. Both temperatures and pH are in the range of *S. obliquus* growth (Difusa et al.,
230 2015; Zhang et al., 2019). During this phase, cell cultures were grown semicontinuously
231 in diluted BBM in 4-L flasks and maintained at a mean cell abundance of approximately
232 $7.5 \times 10^4 \text{ cell mL}^{-1}$.

233

234 **Experimental set up**

235 For the experiment, we aimed to assess the impact of different levels of dust concentration
236 on phytoplankton growth across various combinations of temperature and pH. To achieve
237 this, we established 36 treatments consisting of 3 different temperatures, 3 pH levels, and
238 4 different dust concentration levels (0, 10, 25 and $75 \text{ mg dust L}^{-1}$), each repeated in

239 triplicate. Samples from 4-L flasks were distributed in one hundred and eight - 250 mL
240 Erlenmeyer flasks (36 replicates per temperature and pH and 27 replicates per dust
241 concentration) that were acid-washed before the inoculation of the samples. 36 flasks for
242 each temperature were incubated in their respective environmental chambers. Then, we
243 added dust to each Erlenmeyer flask separately and they were incubated for 7 days at the
244 same conditions of pH and temperature of the acclimation phase. The flasks were shaken
245 twice a day, before the cell abundance measurement and at noon, in order to prevent the
246 sedimentation of *Scenedesmus* cells.

247

248 **Dust collection**

249 Atmospheric deposition samples were collected from five Dry Sampling Units (DSU; see
250 Brahney et al., 2020) located across the western United States in collaboration with the
251 National Atmospheric Deposition Program (NADP). The DSUs are able to recover up to
252 97% of the gravitational dry deposition that enters the sampler (Brahney et al., 2020). To
253 obtain a representative sample of dust deposited over the western United States, dust
254 samples were pooled from 5 locations including Arizona, California, New Mexico, Idaho
255 and Texas (Table S3). The dust used was collected over the spring and summer months
256 of 2021. The amount of dust from each station that was part of the final dust mixture was
257 proportional to the amount of dust deposited in each collector. Thus, the dust collected at
258 the Arizona station in the summer and the Texas station in the spring represented up to
259 40% of the composition of the dust used in our experiment (see Table S3). Since a wide
260 range of dust and phosphorus concentrations is necessary to characterize the
261 phytoplankton response to current and foreseeable future dust inputs, we decided to
262 establish a range from 0 to a maximum concentration of 75 mg dust L⁻¹, corresponding to
263 an event of extreme deposition like the one occurred in the Western Mediterranean and

264 Euro Atlantic region during the winter-spring of 2022 (Cuevas-Agulló et al., 2023). In a
265 previous experiment, this high amount of dust released from 15 to 40 $\mu\text{g P L}^{-1}$, depending
266 on water pH. Nevertheless, the release of P into the environment during actual dust
267 deposition events has been observed within the range of our previous experiment. For
268 instance, Villar-Argaiz et al. (2001) reported an increase in P concentration in Laguna de
269 La Caldera (South Spain) of 23.23 $\mu\text{g P L}^{-1}$ after an external loading event in 1996.
270 Additionally, Brahney et al. (2014), reported higher P concentrations (7-12 $\mu\text{g P L}^{-1}$) in
271 alpine lakes in western Wyoming (USA), exposed to only moderate dust deposition rates
272 compared to nearby lakes with little to no atmospheric deposition. Therefore, the P
273 released by the dust falls within the range of previous and potentially expected P inputs
274 into the aquatic environment following an atmospheric deposition event.

275

276 **Growth rate**

277 Throughout the 7 days of the experiment, we measured the cell abundance for each of the
278 replicates daily, using a 3.5 ml subsample. Subsamples were put into a quartz cuvette and
279 the cell abundance was measured via chlorophyll *a* fluorescence at 436 nm and 680 nm
280 of excitation and emission wavelength, respectively, in a SpectraMax M2 reader
281 (Molecular Devices, Sunnyvale, CA, USA). Growth rate (μ) was calculated from cell
282 abundance as follows:

$$283 \quad \mu = \frac{\ln(C_2) - \ln(C_1)}{t_2 - t_1}$$

284 Where C_j is the cell abundance (cell mL^{-1}) at times t_2 and t_1 . Since some of the treatments
285 reached the peak of cell abundance before others, we used the maximum growth rate
286 calculated throughout the 7 days for each treatment.

287

288 **P cell quota**

289 Subsamples of 15 mL of each flask were filtered at low-pressure through precombusted
290 (1 h at 550°C) glass-fiber filters of 0.7 µm pore size (Whatman GF/F; Whatman®,
291 Sanford, ME, USA). Because nutrient uptake, and consequently cell quota, fluctuate
292 throughout the growth phase of phytoplankton, we measured the P cell quota in each
293 *Scenedesmus* culture at the point of peak abundance. Filters were immediately frozen at
294 -20°C. Elemental P was determined after the filters were digested with a mixture of
295 potassium persulfate and sulfuric acid at 120°C for 30 min and analyzed as soluble
296 reactive P by applying the acid molybdate technique (APHA, 1992).

297

298 **Soluble Reactive Phosphorus (SRP)**

299 After 24 hours of dust addition, 25 mL subsamples of the culture were filtered using the
300 same procedure as for P cell quota. The soluble reactive phosphorus (SRP) concentration
301 in the filtrate was measured on a Lachat QuikChem 8500 Flow Injection analyzer. The
302 method is based on phosphomolybdenum blue method (Murphy & Riley, 1962).

303

304 **Spatial analysis**

305 We carried out a geospatial data analysis in order to detect the continental regions of the
306 planet that will be more affected by atmospheric dust deposition. First, we displayed the
307 planet's soils according to their pH (acidic < 7, neutral = 7, basic > 7) and their cation
308 exchange capacity (CEC; low, 0-15 meq/100 g; medium, 16-25 meq/100 g; high > 26
309 meq/100 g) based on data obtained from the Harmonized World Soil Database (version
310 1.2). We assume that freshwater pH will be related to soil and bedrock pH as well as its
311 CEC. Thus, regions with acidic pH and low CEC will be the most sensitive. We also
312 differentiate between regions with similar pH but different CEC because where the CEC
313 is lower (and, therefore, its capacity to neutralize acids is lower), the environment will be

314 more sensitive to dust inputs. Next, these spatial data were combined with the projections
315 of global temperature increase over the 21st century according to the RCP6.0 scenario
316 (IPCC, 2021). As a result, we represent a map showing those areas of the planet that are
317 sensitive to dust impact. Those areas with low pH and CEC, and high temperature
318 increase, are highly sensitive. Contrarily, those areas with basic pH and high CEC, and
319 lower temperature increases, are the least sensitive.

320

321 Spatial data for areas potentially sensitive to dust deposition (only those with medium
322 sensitivity or higher) were combined with dust deposition data worldwide ($\text{g m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$),
323 obtained from Kok et al. (2021). We have taken into account the natural sources of dust
324 over the world, since they are the most important source of atmospheric P, supplying
325 about 83% of the total global sources of atmospheric P (Mahowald et al., 2008). Finally,
326 we carried out an intersection geospatial analysis for displaying the regions of the planet
327 according to the level of impact of dust, taking into account the soil properties, the
328 foreseeable impact of temperature and atmospheric dust deposition from natural sources.
329 The spatial data analysis was carried out using the QGIS software, Quantum Geographic
330 Information System (version 3.16.15-Hannover, 2020).

331

332 **Statistical analysis**

333 *Nutrient and Growth model*

334 We applied maximum likelihood to fit our nutrient model to the SRP values obtained in
335 our experiment to determine the parameters of our model (see Table S1). We tested three
336 experimental variance models and obtained the best results when the error was assumed
337 to be multiplicative with log-normal distribution. We utilized the fitted nutrient model to
338 predict available phosphorus levels for each of the 36 treatments (3 temperature \times 3 pH

339 × 4 dust treatments). Variance was assumed to be additive with a normal distribution. To
340 eliminate spurious parameter estimates and regularize the error surface, weakly
341 informative priors were multiplied by negative log likelihood. The growth model's
342 parameters were determined using maximum posterior likelihood, which involved
343 computationally minimizing the negative log posterior likelihood (see Table S2).

344

345 *Experimental data*

346 The effect of temperature, pH, dust, and their interaction on all response variables of our
347 experiment (growth rate, SRP and P cell quota) were tested using a factorial analysis of
348 variance (ANOVA). The assumption of normality was verified by the Kolmogorov–
349 Smirnov test and data were logarithmically transformed when assumptions were not
350 satisfied. The differences among treatments were assessed by the post hoc Fisher's least
351 significant differences (LSDs) test when significant interactive effects were found. The
352 analyses were performed with the STATISTICA v7.0 software (Statsoft Inc., 2005).

353

354 The data and model code that support the findings of this study are openly available
355 (González-Olalla et al., 2023; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10081892>).

356

357 **3. Results**

358 **Model results**

359 The growth model shows that under conditions of no dust addition and phosphorus
360 limitation, low pH (6.3) has a negative effect on phytoplankton growth compared to
361 higher pH (6.8 and 7.3; Figure 2 and Figure S2). The lowest pH shows a maximum growth
362 rate of 0.021 d⁻¹ under no dust addition, whereas at 6.8 and 7.3 the maximum growth rate
363 is 0.034 and 0.067 d⁻¹, respectively (Table S4). Optimum temperature (22.1–22.9°C) and

364 thermal tolerance range are similar for the three pH levels under no dust addition.
365 However, our model shows that as the dust concentration increases: a) the maximum
366 growth of *S. obliquus* increases from values ranging 0.021-0.067 d⁻¹ under no dust
367 addition to 0.192-0.223 d⁻¹ in treatments with 75 mg dust L⁻¹; b) the thermal tolerance
368 range widens for all pH values, being this greater at pH 6.3 due to a higher phosphorus
369 availability. Thus, the combination of low pH and high dust concentration (75 mg L⁻¹)
370 results in the widest range of thermal tolerance and growth rate for *S. obliquus*, so the
371 thermal range increased from an upper thermal limit of 27°C under no dust addition to
372 30°C under highest dust addition and lowest pH; c) the negative effect of low pH at low
373 dust concentrations shifts to a positive effect at high dust concentrations and high
374 temperatures; d) the optimum temperature progressively increases with dust addition,
375 from similar values for all the pH treatments under no dust addition to a maximum
376 optimum temperature (24.7°C) under 75 mg dust L⁻¹ addition and pH 6.3 (see Figure 2,
377 Figure S2 and Table S4).

378

379 **Experimental results**

380 The addition of dust led to a progressive increase in the soluble reactive phosphorous
381 (SRP) concentration for all the temperature and pH treatments (Figure 3 and Table S5;
382 $p < 0.05$). Furthermore, there is a trend towards a greater SRP availability when the pH
383 drops from 7.3 to 6.3 for each temperature treatment (Figure 3). Consequently, the,
384 average SRP values after the addition of 75 mg dust L⁻¹ ranged from 14-17 $\mu\text{g P L}^{-1}$ at
385 pH 7.3 to 30-45 $\mu\text{g P L}^{-1}$ at pH 6.3. These results align with the pattern expected from our
386 nutrient model. As a result, our predicted phosphorous concentrations in our nutrient
387 model fit well to our SRP results at 3 temperatures, 3 pH and 4 dust conditions ($R^2 =$
388 0.903; Figure 1b).

389

390 The growth rate of *S. obliquus* was stimulated by an increase in dust for all temperature
391 and pH treatments (Figure 4 and Table S5; $p < 0.05$). In regards to the effect of
392 temperature, our analysis of variance shows that there is a slight stimulation in the growth
393 rate of *S. obliquus* from 19°C to 23°C. However, the treatments at 27°C exert an overall
394 negative impact on the growth rate ($p < 0.05$; Table S5). Furthermore *S. obliquus* exhibited
395 a higher growth rate at pH of 6.3 and 7.3 than at pH 6.8 ($p < 0.05$; Table S5). As result of
396 these single factor effects, we observed a shift in the response pattern. Thus, at low
397 temperatures, there is a positive effect of high pH (7.3) on the growth rate compared to
398 lower pH (6.8 and 6.3). As temperature increases, this pattern shifts towards a higher
399 growth rate when pH decreases to 6.3 (Figure 4). In this way, growth rate values are
400 higher at pH 6.3 when temperature reaches 27°C. Moreover, our results show that
401 negative effect of high temperature on growth rate is reverted when high dust
402 concentration ($\geq 25 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) is added under low pH (6.3; Figure 4). The growth rate data
403 from our experiment are fit to our growth model ($R^2 = 0.691$; see Figure 1c).

404

405 The phosphorus cell quotas ranged from approximately 500 fg P cell⁻¹ to ~2400 fg P cell⁻¹
406 (see Figure 5). Overall, the results demonstrated a significant increase of P cell quota
407 with higher dust additions, except for a few treatments with 25 or 75 mg dust L⁻¹. Similar
408 to the growth rate pattern, P cell quota increases with higher pH under the low-
409 temperature treatment (19°C), whereas this pattern is reversed at high temperature (27°C)
410 with higher P cell quota observed under lower pH (Figure 5). Moreover, the treatments
411 with high temperatures (27°C) and low pH (6.3) lead to higher P cell quota in *S. obliquus*
412 after dust addition (Figure 5).

413

414 **Global impact of dust depending on soil sensitivity and warming**

415 Our geospatial analysis predicts the impact of atmospheric dust deposition on inland
416 aquatic ecosystems (Figure 6). Based on global dust deposition rates (Figure 6a, see
417 Figure S3 for more detail) and the potential sensitivity of soils to dust deposition (Figure
418 6b, see Figure S4 and S5 for more detail) some areas in the western United States, South
419 America, central and southern Africa and Asia, central Australia as well as the
420 Mediterranean region will be highly or very highly impacted by dust deposition (Figure
421 6c, see Figure S6 for more detail of each continent). These areas are characterized by high
422 dust deposition, soils very sensitive with $\text{pH} \leq 6.5$ or low cation exchange capacity, and
423 the forecast of a high temperature increase compared to other areas. Some areas with
424 sensitive aquatic systems that are expected to experience strong temperature increases
425 were not determined to be especially sensitive owing to low dust deposition rates. In
426 contrast, some regions in northern Africa and the Arabian peninsula show a very low or
427 zero impact of dust despite the high dust deposition due to the high pH of these soils
428 (≥ 7.5).

429

430 **4. Discussion**

431 Our study investigates the role of dust-derived nutrients in stimulating phytoplankton
432 growth and how dust affects their thermal and pH tolerance ranges. We develop a novel
433 model for phytoplankton growth and test it using empirical data from a controlled
434 experiment with *Scenedesmus obliquus*. The experiment included three temperature
435 levels, three pH levels, and four dust concentrations. Our ecological model provides
436 valuable insights into the future dynamics of phytoplankton populations and their
437 responses to environmental conditions. We also forecast the potential impact of dust on

438 freshwater ecosystems in continental areas, taking into account their sensitivity to acid
439 deposition, soil pH, and the effects of global warming.

440

441 **Dust effect on growth**

442 The positive effect of dust on *S. obliquus* growth rate and abundance observed in our
443 study (P-limited environment; NP molar ratio = 75) is consistent with real world
444 observational studies, and likely related to the alleviation of phosphorus (P) limitation
445 (Camarero & Catalan, 2012), highlighting the potential of dust as a driver of primary
446 production and phytoplankton growth (Ballantyne et al., 2011; Morales-Baquero et al.,
447 2006), particularly in freshwater ecosystems of the western United States (Brahney et al.,
448 2015a), southern Europe (Cabrerizo et al., 2017; González-Olalla et al., 2018), as well as
449 increasing phytoplankton biomass (Stockdale et al., 2016) and Chl *a* in marine areas of
450 the Mediterranean sea (Gallisai et al., 2014; González-Olalla et al., 2017) South China
451 Sea (Chu et al., 2018), or Tropical Atlantic Ocean and Southern Ocean (Barkley et al.,
452 2019).

453

454 Our experiment revealed a complex relationship between temperature, pH, and dust
455 concentration that aligns for the most part with the Growth Rate Hypothesis, and
456 highlights the importance of considering nutrient limitation and cellular processes in
457 understanding the responses of microalgae to environmental changes. The Growth Rate
458 hypothesis (Sterner & Elser, 2002) predicts that there is a positive relationship between
459 maximum growth rate and P-rich RNA (expressed as g⁻¹ dry weight). This positive
460 relationship has been corroborated in successive studies with eukaryotic photosynthetic
461 organisms, including freshwater microalgae ($R^2 = 0.66$; Rees & Raven, 2021). We found
462 a similar pattern between the growth rate of *S. obliquus* and P cell quota, increasing from

463 low to high pH at low temperature, and from high to low pH at the highest temperature.
464 Remarkably, *S. obliquus* growing at 27°C, pH 6.3 and under dust addition of 75 mg dust
465 L⁻¹ showed the highest P cell quota in agreement with the highest growth rate. However,
466 we found this relationship did not always hold true. Some treatments of 25 and 75 mg
467 dust L⁻¹ did not show a higher P cell-quota according to a higher growth rate. We think
468 that there are two possible explanations: that a high rate of cell division under these
469 conditions can lead to high growth but also a lower amount of P per cell (Hoppe et al.,
470 2018; Thompson et al., 1992; Wolf et al., 2018); or that the increased competitive ability
471 of the bacteria present in the environment to acquire and store nutrients (Sterner et al.,
472 2004) may have affected the availability of P for *Scenedesmus*. In nature, if the demand
473 for P by the bacteria in the aquatic environment exceeds the P supplied by the dust, there
474 could be a decrease in the magnitude of phytoplankton's response (Tanaka et al., 2006).
475 However, in our experiment, the SRP values and *Scenedesmus* growth rate increased as
476 the dust concentration in the medium increased, so we do not expect *Scenedesmus's*
477 response to be conditioned by a high demand for P by the bacteria. In any case, we
478 consider that changes in the magnitude of the phytoplankton response would not alter its
479 direction or pattern of response.

480

481 On the other hand, it's important to note that composition of the dust sample used in our
482 experiment and its effects on phytoplankton growth are representative of events in other
483 parts of the planet. The phosphorus content in our sample (1113.86 mg P kg⁻¹; 0.11% of
484 P relative to the dust) falls within the intermediate range of Sahara Desert dust samples
485 (0.022% - 0.6%; see Gross et al., 2015, 2016, 2021; Guieu et al., 2002), similar to
486 Colorado dust (0.055-0.091%; see Lawrence et al., 2010; Zhang et al., 2018), and very
487 close to the mean concentration determined by Lawrence and Neff (2009) for 10 samples

488 of dust deposited in different regions of the planet ($1086.6 \text{ mg P kg}^{-1}$), or even lower than
489 Negev Desert dust (0.41-1.2%; see Gross et al., 2021; Uni & Katra, 2017), as well as dust
490 enriched with ashes from wildfires (0.77-0.84%; see Tiwari et al., 2022), or dust collected
491 near urban areas in Pakistan (1.6%; Shafqat et al., 2016). Furthermore, the fraction of
492 bioavailable phosphorus over the total phosphorus, on average, was 30% in our dust,
493 compared to 15% in North African aerosols (Dam et al., 2021) and 54% in European
494 aerosols (Longo et al., 2014). Anderson et al. (2010) found that 15-30% of the phosphorus
495 contained in dust from the Gulf of Aqaba was bioavailable. In the Negev Desert, this
496 fraction only represented 8% of the total phosphorus (Gross et al., 2021), while in areas
497 of Pakistan (Shafqat et al., 2016), the amount of bioavailable phosphorus exceeded that
498 of our dust sample (895 mg kg^{-1} in Pakistan vs. 397 mg kg^{-1} in our dust; see Table S3).
499 Therefore, considering the area covered by our collectors ($\approx 3 \cdot 10^6 \text{ km}^2$), the duration of
500 the dust collection period (6 months, Spring-Summer), the various sources of dust
501 emissions that our collectors are capable of capturing (deserts, urban areas, wildfires),
502 and the P richness of our dust sample, which is the primary limiting nutrient for
503 phytoplankton growth in our experiment and most of freshwater ecosystems, we believe
504 that the dust employed in our experiment provides a reasonably accurate approximation
505 of its actual effects on freshwater phytoplankton.

506

507 In essence, we anticipate observing a similar response pattern, with variations in
508 magnitude of effect (but not in direction), depending on the nutrient content of the dust.
509 Despite that, we should note that in some cases dust could have a negative effect on
510 phytoplankton growth if the presence of toxic metals outweighs the benefits of nutrient
511 inputs (Paytan et al., 2009).

512

513 **Dust effect on thermal and pH tolerance range**

514 One of our most compelling findings is that dust can play a critical role in broadening the
515 environmental tolerances of phytoplanktonic organisms. Specifically, we found that dust
516 is able to exert a positive effect on increasing the range of thermal and pH tolerance in a
517 commonly found freshwater phytoplankton species, *S. obliquus*. In our experiments, *S.*
518 *obliquus* showed the highest growth rate at 23°C, but its growth significantly declined at
519 27°C. Our growth model also shows that the optimum growth temperature ranged
520 between 22-23°C under conditions of no dust addition. These results would agree with
521 previous authors who have shown a greater growth of *Scenedesmus* around 25°C (see
522 Yang et al., 2018). Remarkably, when we added increasing concentrations of dust the
523 optimum temperature was increased and thermal tolerance widened for all the pH
524 conditions (see Figure 2 and Table S4). Thus, optimum temperature (and upper thermal
525 limit) in our Growth model varied from 22.94°C (27°C) under no dust addition to 24.66°C
526 (30°C) after addition of 75 mg dust L⁻¹ at pH 6.3. Similar changes but of lower magnitude
527 were observed for pH 6.8 and 7.3. In our experiment, the addition of dust (75 mg L⁻¹)
528 counteracted the negative effect of high temperature and low pH and stimulated *S.*
529 *obliquus* growth showing positive values at 27°C for all the pH conditions. Nutrient
530 availability and temperature are key environmental factors that control phytoplankton
531 growth and they can act synergistically stimulating the algal biomass (Fernández-
532 González et al., 2022). Ectothermic organisms that exhibit increasing performance as
533 temperature increases must also be able to supply nutrients and other resources to keep
534 the high demand of biological rates (Kefford et al., 2022). If nutrient resources increase
535 simultaneously to temperature increase, then optimum temperature for growth will
536 increase and also the upper thermal limit will increase (Huey & Kingsolver, 2019).
537 Therefore, nutrients contained in dust can supply the energy and nutritional building

538 blocks so that phytoplankton is able to cope with temperature increase. In agreement with
539 our results, Thomas et al. (2017) showed that higher concentration of nutrients leads to a
540 broader thermal tolerance of the marine *Thalassiosira pseudonana*, and Bestion et al.
541 (2018) reported that those findings can be generalized to six other freshwater
542 phytoplankton species, including *S. obliquus*.

543

544 Our results also indicate that dust addition was able to increase the pH tolerance in *S.*
545 *obliquus*. Under the no dust addition treatment, our results support the conclusion that a
546 slightly alkaline environment is more favorable for the *Scenedesmus* growth (Al-Shatri
547 Hussein et al., 2014; Gardner et al., 2011). Other studies have reported that a pH decrease
548 exerts a negative effect on *S. obliquus* biomass in the range of 6-8 (Zhang et al., 2019).
549 Therefore, in agreement with our growth model, we should expect a lower growth at pH
550 6.3 than at 7.3. In fact, *S. obliquus* growing at 19°C and no dust addition exhibited a
551 significantly lower growth rate at pH 6.3 and 6.8 than at pH 7.3. However, when dust was
552 introduced, our results show that the negative effect of low pH on phytoplankton growth
553 becomes positive under high dust deposition (75 mg dust L⁻¹) and high temperature, due
554 to the positive effect of warming and nutrient availability on phytoplankton growth.
555 Furthermore, the optimum temperature for growth and thermal tolerance exhibited a
556 greater increase as the pH decreased from 7.3 to 6.3 and dust concentration increased
557 from 0 to 75 mg L⁻¹. Our results for *Scenedesmus* confirmed that at 27°C and a pH of 6.8
558 or 6.3, the highest addition of dust exerted a positive effect on growth rate, counteracting
559 the negative effect of pH 6.8 on phytoplankton under no dust addition and showed the
560 highest growth rate at pH 6.3 for all the treatments.

561

562 It is possible that the greater availability of P at low pH could explain a synergistic
563 interaction between temperature and nutrients. In fact, our nutrient model, supported by
564 the dust P release results obtained in our experiment, show that a decrease in pH led to
565 higher available P concentrations for each dust and temperature treatment (Figure 3).
566 Previous research has indicated that acidic conditions during the transport of dust in the
567 atmosphere can increase the bioavailability of P, thereby increasing the potential for dust
568 to exert a strong effect in oligotrophic ecosystems (Baker & Croot, 2010; Stockdale et al.,
569 2016). Additionally, when a scarcity of inorganic phosphorus coincides with a mildly
570 acidic pH, it can promote the stimulation of acid phosphatase activity (optimal pH 4-6),
571 further increasing the bioavailability of P (Hoppe, 2003). While the pH reduction applied
572 in our experiment does not reach the acidity levels associated with extreme levels of
573 sulfuric and nitric acid in the atmosphere, our findings demonstrate that a pH decrease of
574 0.5-1 units in aquatic ecosystems was able to increase the P released from dust. In
575 contrast, Dinasquet et al. (2022) reported that a pH decrease of 0.3 units under warming
576 conditions did not affect the amount of nutrient released from dust. However, their
577 experiment was carried out with a marine community, so it is possible that a high initial
578 pH of the seawater (~8.2) combined with a limited decrease of pH compared to our
579 experiment affected the nutrient release. That means that because freshwater ecosystems
580 have in general lower pH and buffering capacity, particularly when they are significantly
581 affected by acid deposition, they can experience greater impacts from dust inputs. Despite
582 the main goal of this study being to assess how initial pH conditions can affect nutrient
583 release from dust and its subsequent impact on algal growth, we should also mention that
584 dust, often rich in alkaline constituents, can alter pH levels in aquatic ecosystems
585 (Brahney et al., 2014, 2021; Rogora et al., 2004), leading to changes in the carbonate
586 system and nutrient availability that could influence phytoplankton growth (Galotti et al.,

587 2018). However, this falls outside the scope of our study and undoubtedly warrants further
588 consideration in future models and experiments.

589

590 Our innovative study examines the interactions between dust, pH and warming. We
591 demonstrate that in aquatic systems experiencing high dust inputs and warming
592 conditions, a decrease in pH of up to 1 unit can exert a positive effect on phytoplankton
593 attributed to an extra release of nutrients available for growth. In contrast, a previous
594 study by Murphy et al. (2020) showed a negative effect on phytoplankton from rock pools
595 when subjected to warming (+8°C) and acidification of 0.8 units. In our research, we not
596 only corroborate the role of dust increasing the thermal range and temperature optimum
597 in phytoplankton, but we also demonstrate that a negative effect of lower pH under low
598 nutrient concentrations can be transformed to a positive effect due to a higher release of
599 nutrients from dust under more acidic conditions. This interaction becomes particularly
600 significant when combined with higher temperatures, broadening the pH range suitable
601 for growth and influencing the competitive ability of different phytoplankton species
602 (Hansen, 2002). It is important to note that this positive effect of the pH has a species-
603 specific limit that corresponds to their pH tolerance range (Hinga, 2002). A more
604 substantial decrease of pH could have detrimental consequences on cellular functioning
605 that would not be compensated for an excess of nutrients. In essence, while the theoretical
606 growth curves of phytoplankton in response to these factors are common across species,
607 and thus show a realistic approximation of our study, the different optimal ranges for
608 temperature, pH, and nutrients are species-specific and reinforce the need for further
609 research involving a larger number of key phytoplankton species.

610

611 **Dust effect on a global scale**

612 Geospatial modeling indicates that areas of the planet most vulnerable to atmospheric
613 dust deposition are generally situated near arid and semi-arid areas, especially if the land
614 is degraded or under unsustainable use (Ginoux et al., 2012). Therefore, regions such as
615 the western United States, areas near the Atacama Desert in South America, central and
616 southern Africa and Asia, central Australia as well as the Mediterranean region will be
617 highly or very highly impacted by dust deposition.

618

619 Our experimental results suggest that the impact of dust on continental aquatic
620 ecosystems, and more specifically on phytoplankton, will be determined by the amount
621 and composition of dust, the degree of oligotrophy of the water (Marañón et al., 2010;
622 Marín-Beltrán et al., 2019), the initial composition and metabolic state of the investigated
623 community (Gazeau et al., 2021), as well as by the characteristics of the underlying
624 ecosystems (e.g., soil properties including pH, cation exchange capacity or bedrock;
625 Likens et al., 1996; Nadelhoffer et al., 1999). Therefore, the spatial variability of
626 freshwater conditions will determine the magnitude of dust impact to lake ecosystems.
627 Though our geospatial analysis could not directly determine the metabolic state of each
628 lake, we used the geologic properties of the basins to estimate the natural condition and
629 thus the future impact of increasing temperature and dust additions. Because
630 physicochemical factors of aquatic ecosystems, such as pH, strongly affect P behavior
631 after dust deposition, we found that areas with calcareous bedrock, and hence higher pH
632 (Lazzaro et al., 2009; Mosher & Findlay, 2011), required more dust addition to alter the
633 aquatic community than sites in more siliceous bedrock (Figure 6). While most of the P
634 contained in Saharan dust is released in the Amazon basin due to its highly acidic soils
635 (pH 4.17–4.94) (De Négreiros & Nepstad, 1994), only 15–30% of P reaching the Gulf of
636 Aqaba (Anderson et al., 2010) is released from dust because of the alkaline seawater (pH

637 ≈ 8.2). Accordingly, basins with low pH or low CEC, and where a strong increase of
638 temperature is expected were potentially very sensitive to dust impacts.

639

640 Climate projections suggest that current dusty regions are likely to experience a decrease
641 in precipitation, including the southwest of United States, southern Australia,
642 Mediterranean area, northern Sahara and central Asia (Christensen et al., 2007).
643 Furthermore, drought conditions and landscape disturbance will increase dust emissions
644 to the atmosphere as well, due to its effect on soil moisture and vegetation coverage
645 (Munson et al., 2011; Prospero & Lamb, 2003). Therefore, our analysis allows us to point
646 out the areas of the planet that may be exposed to a greater impact of dust, altering the
647 functioning of the dynamics of populations and ecosystems in those regions.

648

649 **5. Conclusions**

650 Our work attempts, for the first time, to analyze and describe the complex interaction of
651 how the foreseeable increase of dust storms and the input of nutrients to aquatic
652 ecosystems can interact together with temperature and pH leading to a regulation of the
653 phytoplankton growth rate growing in freshwater aquatic communities. Our empirical
654 results and our mechanistic model show that dust storms are capable of stimulating
655 phytoplankton growth and that high intensity storms can broaden the range of thermal
656 and pH tolerance in the phytoplankton. Thus, phytoplanktonic organisms located in
657 ecosystems where dust deposition can supply limiting nutrients (e.g., phosphorus) may
658 show a greater capacity for acclimation under future conditions of higher temperatures
659 and low pH. This response is possible because phytoplankton can utilize the additional
660 nutrient supply resulting from a slight drop in pH, combined with high temperatures, to
661 promote their growth. Our findings emphasize the importance of comprehending the

662 factors that regulate phytoplankton population dynamics and employing mechanistic
663 models to explain and interpret these responses. Furthermore, our research illustrates how
664 dust can impact the organisms at the foundation of aquatic food webs, influencing the
665 role of aquatic ecosystems in biogeochemical cycles (e.g., carbon sink) and the
666 management of biological resources in highly dust-sensitive aquatic ecosystems.

667

668 **Acknowledgements**

669 This study was supported by National Science Foundation (2011910 and 1926559 to
670 J.B.). J.M.G.-O. was supported by the National Science Foundation project 2011910 and
671 1926559. The authors are grateful to Audree Provard for her help in the analysis of soluble
672 reactive phosphorus and Karin Kettenring for letting us use the environmental chambers
673 for the experiment.

674 The authors declare no competing interests.

675

676 **Author contribution**

677 Experiment conceptualization: Juan Manuel González Olalla and Janice Brahney.
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680 James A Powell. Model analysis: James A Powell. Visualization: Juan Manuel González
681 Olalla and James A Powell. Supervision: James A Powell and Janice Brahney. Funding
682 acquisition: Janice Brahney. Writing-review and editing: Juan Manuel González-Olalla,
683 James A Powell and Janice Brahney.

684

685 **Data availability**

686 The data and model code that support the findings of this study are openly available in
687 Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10081892>, reference number 10081892.

688

689

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1103

1104 **Figure Legends**

1105 Figure 1. (a) Nutrient model prediction for phosphorus released from dust ($\mu\text{g P L}^{-1}$) at
 1106 different pH and 20°C; (b) Predicted vs. observed available phosphorus ($\mu\text{g P L}^{-1}$) after
 1107 24 hours of dust addition ($R^2 = 0.903$) under three temperature levels (19, 23 and 27°C),
 1108 three pH levels (6.3, 6.8 and 7.3) and four dust concentrations (0, 10, 25, 75 mg L^{-1}). Note
 1109 that the plot of predictions against observations illustrates the growth of variance with
 1110 predicted phosphorus, consistent with the multiplicative log normal model for
 1111 observational variance; (c) Predicted vs. observed maximum growth rate ($R^2 = 0.691$)

1112 under three temperature levels (19, 23 and 27°C), three pH levels (6.3, 6.8 and 7.3) and
1113 four dust concentrations (0, 10, 25, 75 mg L⁻¹).

1114

1115 Figure 2. Growth rate (day⁻¹) model for *Scenedesmus obliquus* under a gradient of dust
1116 (mg L⁻¹), temperature (°C), and pH 6.3 (a), 6.8 (b) and 7.3 (c). Dust concentrations are
1117 showed in the left y-axis, growth rate values in the right y-axis, and temperature values
1118 in the x-axis. Green lines represent the limits for thermal tolerance of phytoplankton,
1119 whereas the blue line represent the optimum temperature for phytoplankton growth.
1120 Please note that the growth rate is indicated by the color gradient, which increases towards
1121 the upper right corner of the box, shown in yellow-white.

1122

1123 Figure 3. Soluble Reactive Phosphorus (SRP, µg P L⁻¹) after 24 hours of dust addition
1124 under different treatments of temperature (19°C, 23°C, 27°C), pH (6.3, 6.8, 7.3), and dust
1125 concentration (0, 10, 25, and 75 mg L⁻¹). Data are expressed as mean values ± SD (n =
1126 3).

1127

1128 Figure 4. Maximum growth rate (day⁻¹) of *Scenedesmus obliquus* under different
1129 treatments of temperature (19°C, 23°C, 27°C), pH (6.3, 6.8, 7.3), and dust concentration
1130 (0, 10, 25, and 75 mg L⁻¹). Data are expressed as mean values ± SD (n = 3).

1131

1132 Figure 5. Phosphorous cell quota (fg P cell⁻¹) in *Scenedesmus obliquus* under different
1133 treatments of temperature (19°C, 23°C, 27°C), pH (6.3, 6.8, 7.3), and dust concentration
1134 (0, 10, 25, and 75 mg L⁻¹). Data are expressed as mean values ± SD (n = 3).

1135

1136 Figure 6. Composition of maps for world spatial analysis using mineral dust deposition
1137 ($\text{g m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$) obtained from Kok et al. (2021), where intensely red-colored regions
1138 indicate higher dust depositions (a); world regions potentially sensitive to dust inputs,
1139 where red-brown regions are more sensitive than yellow-green regions (b; see Supporting
1140 Information Figures S2-S5); and impact of dust in different regions (c) obtained from
1141 combination of map “a” and “b”.

1 Figures

2 Figure 1. (a) Nutrient model prediction for phosphorus released from dust at different pH
3 and 20°C; (b) Predicted vs. observed available phosphorus after 24 hours of dust addition
4 ($R^2 = 0.903$) under three temperature levels, three pH levels and four dust concentrations.
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6 with predicted phosphorus, consistent with the multiplicative log normal model for
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38 ($\text{g m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$) obtained from Kok et al., 2021 (a); world regions potentially sensitive to
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40 map A and B (see Supporting Information Figures S2-S5).

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